

STAGES OF THE INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. THE SPECIFICS OF PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIONS. HOW IT MANIFESTS ITSELF WHEN TEACHING PHYSICAL CULTURE

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RESUME. Pedagogical innovations in the broadest interpretation affect the entire education system and its individual components. Education is predominantly an artificial, projected and constructed object. The normative sphere of education, its technological level includes the following main components: the draft of the educational course (curriculum, program, general recommendations of the educational organization); the description of the educational course or pedagogical descriptions (normative descriptions of ideal and material means of education); an educational course as a set of pedagogical prescriptions. These three components are the objects of innovative transformations.

Key words: knowledge, pedagogical technologies, physical culture, methods.

At the same time, all possible pedagogical innovations presuppose their radical change and (or) improvement, modification, since the final project of education is a course consisting of pedagogical prescriptions. The specificity of pedagogical innovation is determined by a combination of factors. First of all, the fact that education is an artificial, sociotechnical or social system. The sociotechnical system is characterized by the presence of people and collectives in it, whose interests are significantly related to its functioning. As a result of the participation of people, the dominant connections in such systems do not belong to nature, but to culture, and the meaning of any situation is determined by the

attitude of the subject to it. In sociotechnical systems, the subjective prevails over the objective, the heuristic over the formal. These systems change over time both by themselves and as a result of exposure to them. The presence of a humanitarian component in pedagogical innovations presupposes their rigid boundaries. Any pedagogical innovation should be considered in the context of preserving the health of the child and the teacher, taking into account the long-term consequences. The specificity of pedagogical innovation is also generated by the lack of certain evaluation criteria for the effectiveness of teaching and upbringing processes, in particular, reasonable specific recommendations. In this regard, N. V. Kukharev, noting the relevance of the formulation of this issue, pointed out its complexity, the need to rethink the evaluation method that has become a postulate, when a teacher's work is qualified by an "effectively" conducted lesson.

The analysis of pedagogical innovations also showed that their natural development is not always adequate to the classical life cycle. Many pedagogical innovations do not "die", as it happens, for example, with technical innovations, and do not integrate with other searches, but simply move from the position of actual, "first roles" on the stage of pedagogical reality, to the position of potentially possible ones. Their existence is more adequate to the logic of culture than to the logic of cognition.

Pedagogical innovations are plural vectors of the development of pedagogical reality, "live" on the didactic stage simultaneously for objective and/or subjective reasons, changing their roles. The world "for the first time" in the development of didactic reality through innovations fully complements its cumulative component and the classical life cycle of innovations. Thus, an ideal pedagogical innovation is a holistic problem-oriented process of conjugate changes in the entire educational course or its individual components (pedagogical prescriptions) and the environment of innovation (means and conditions of education), which lead to an increase in the efficiency and quality of

education.

Innovative educational processes are based on two major problems of pedagogy: the problem of studying pedagogical experience and the problem of bringing this experience to practice.

The topic of innovations in the pedagogical activity of physical education teachers is very relevant at the moment, so teachers introduce new teaching methods to interest students. I use the following innovative technologies in my lessons:

- health-saving and developing technologies;
- designing the educational environment of the lesson using modern pedagogical teaching technologies;
- designing a comfortable adaptive environment (more freedom, emancipation, creativity of students in the classroom);
- information and communication technologies.

Innovations in the system of physical education of the student are a functional necessity of teachers of educational institutions. The use of innovative technologies in physical education is primarily a creative approach to the pedagogical process in order to increase interest in physical education and sports. This is the main goal that we strive for in connection with the task of increasing the level of the learning process to preserve health.

Factors (forces) contributing to innovations in education. Types of innovators.

Innovation as a process has an internal logic and direction. It unfolds from the idea of innovation to its use by the consumer, taking into account the logic of relations between the participants in the process, which is called the innovation process. There are two forms of the innovation process: a) simple reproduction of innovation, characterized by the fact that the innovation is made only in the organization where it was mastered; b) extended reproduction of innovation involves its spread to many organizations.

At the intra-organizational level, the following factors are identified that hinder and promote innovation: the structure of the organization; the system of statuses and social prestige; the system of interests, incentives and motives of work; management style and methods, socio-psychological climate in the team. At the level of the individual (personality), the values; attitudes; motives; roles of the participants of the innovation; the opportunities that this participation opens up for their social advancement and creative development of the personality as a whole are significant. The sources of the constantly emerging problems of introducing a new one include the following contradictions: change and stability; the volume of consequences; the multiplicity of the object; the mismatch of innovation processes, the gap between the initial and final stages of innovation; the separation of the "pioneer" introduction from the mass, etc. Obstacles to innovation can be caused by the following factors: the nature of the proposed innovation (relative profitability, compatibility, complexity, phasing, sociability); the approach to the emergence and implementation of innovation (if recipients are not aware of the ways of creating, developing and implementing innovation, then this may determine the obstacles in its path; therefore, they should actively participate at all stages of innovation); the relationship of innovators and managers between themselves and other participants of innovation. The successful implementation of innovation is based on three main principles: 1 The principle of organic connection of the emergence, development and implementation of innovations. 2 The principle of planned integration of innovation with the object on which it is implemented. 3 The principle of active support of higher-level links.

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educational course (curriculum, program, general recommendations of the educational organization); the description of the educational course or pedagogical descriptions (normative descriptions of ideal and material means of education); an educational course as a set of pedagogical prescriptions. These three components are the objects of innovative transformations. At the same time, all possible pedagogical innovations presuppose their radical change and (or) improvement, modification, since the final project of education is a course consisting of pedagogical prescriptions.

In South Korea, for example, they started using robot teachers, they work with children, teaching them English. The robot is controlled by a native speaker teacher online. This made it possible to solve the problem of shortage of personnel in Korea.

An alternative school system has been practiced in Finland for several years. Based on the educational program, teachers themselves can choose the style of work with students that they consider the most appropriate. There is no rating system. Of course, such a system assumes a high qualification of the teachers themselves.

Innovation is based on a practical idea found on the basis of empirical knowledge, through the method of "trial and error" or at the level of common sense. There are different classifications of innovators. By the nature of innovation activity, creators and implementers are distinguished. The former are the authors of innovations, and the latter organize the process of its development. In relation to the main specialty, professional and amateur innovators are distinguished. Types of Innovators: 1. Entrepreneur (a manager who supports and promotes an idea (possibly his own)). 2. An idea generator (Issues a large number of original proposals in a short time, strives to solve complex problems). 3. Gatekeeper (Captures and processes fresh ideas, accumulates and transmits progressive experience). 4. Moderator of ideas (Critic of new scientific

information). 5. Animator of ideas (Notices the strengths of a new idea, supports the idea generator). In the innovation process, the position of the head of the organization where the innovation is implemented is important. In relation to the innovation process, there are five types of managers: conservative, declarative, hesitant, progressive, obsessive.

The essence of the technological approach in teaching. Technologies of developing learning. Developing learning technologies that can be used in teaching physical culture.

In the 70s, the impact of a systematic approach gradually led to the general attitude of pedagogical technology: to solve didactic problems in the course of managing the educational process with precisely set goals, the achievement of which should be clearly described and defined.

Pedagogical technology is a set of psychological and pedagogical attitudes that define a special set of forms and methods, methods, techniques of teaching.

The technological approach to learning aims to construct the learning process, starting from the given initial settings (social order, educational guidelines, goals and content of training). The specificity of pedagogical technology is that the educational process in it should guarantee the achievement of the set goals. The basis of consistent orientation of learning towards goals is operational feedback, which permeates the entire learning process. In accordance with this , the technological approach to training highlights:

1. Setting goals and their maximum refinement, formulation of educational goals with a focus on achieving results.
2. Preparation of educational materials and organization of the entire course of study in accordance with the educational objectives.
3. Assessment of current results, correction of training aimed at achieving the set goals.
4. Final evaluation of the results.

For an objective assessment of the quality of the results of any high-tech products or services, which undoubtedly include educational and scientific and methodological services of the school, in addition to assessing the degree of compliance of the results of the technological process with the requirements, it is also necessary to have a conclusion about the quality of the process of providing these services. In other words, how perfect, orderly, organized, secured and aimed at preventing the occurrence of deviations, inconsistencies, etc. Thus, the quality of the results of schools' activities should be ensured through quality management of the main work processes taking place in the school.

Developmental learning is the orientation of the educational process to the potential capabilities of a person and their reaction. The purpose of this type of education is to prepare students for the independent development of knowledge, the search for truth, as well as for independence in everyday life. That is, it is based on the formation of thinking mechanisms, and not on the exploitation of memory. Students should master the mental operations by which knowledge is assimilated and operated on. Developmental learning is learning, the content, methods and forms of organization of which are based on the patterns of child development.

The theory of developmental learning originates in the works of I.G. Pestalozzi, A. Disterveg, K.D. Ushinsky, L.S. Vygotsky, L.V. Zankov, V.V. Davydov, etc.

The following signs of learning technology are distinguished: 1) the joint activity of the teacher and the child; 2) a set of techniques, methods; 3) the design and organization of the learning process; 4) the availability of comfortable conditions for the disclosure, realization and development of the personal potential of the child.

Any learning technology includes: a target orientation; scientific ideas on which it is based; systems of actions of the teacher and the student; criteria for

evaluating the result; results; limitations in use. In the technology of developmental learning, the child is assigned the role of an independent subject interacting with the environment. This interaction includes all stages of activity: goal setting, planning and organization, implementation of goals and analysis of performance results. Each of the stages makes its own specific contribution to the development of personality.

The principles underlying the technology of developmental learning:

- there is no development outside of activity;
- students' knowledge of their own abilities and the results of the teaching are mandatory conditions for their further mental development;
- a student becomes a subject of educational activity only on the basis of such personal self-education as activity, independence and communication.

Conditions of achievement.

1. Organization of the educational space on the basis of the leading concepts of the theory of developing learning "educational activity and its subject"; Construction of the educational space as a space of the student's orientation activity due to the movement from conception – to testing – completion – to decision – to action;

2. Creating conditions for individualization of learning by giving students the opportunity to freely choose ways and means to solve their own educational tasks, choosing the "space" of activity;

3. Active use of interactive technologies in pedagogical practice: methods of productive dialogue and project activities, information computer technologies;

4. Mastering the new pedagogical position of the "pedagogical manager";

5. The use of various sources of information in the educational process, including textbooks by different authors, the creation of their own methodological tools that allow students to organize productive individual and independent activities;

6. Merging of academic and extracurricular activities.

During the main part of the lesson, I use various game methods. One of them is integrated games. The features of such games are that the contests, quizzes, riddles, competitions, various texts used in them are selected and compiled in such a way that they contribute to the education of patriotism, a sense of camaraderie, duty, rules of a healthy lifestyle, the basics of life safety, etiquette. Plot-role-playing games that develop their creativity and imagination are also interesting for children. Frequent change of activities. A variety of forms of lesson organization, alternating mental and physical activity of students is one of their ways to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. Periodicity of theory and practice. Favorable friendly atmosphere in the classroom. The lesson should be educational and interesting. During the lesson, I always pay attention to the physical and psychological state of the children, I look at how they perceive the teacher's tasks, how they evaluate his work. I make demands and comments only in a friendly way. Differentiated approach to each child. Educational orientation of the lesson. The educational effect of physical education lessons is also achieved due to the possibilities of an individually differentiated approach to the development of the qualities of each student and the formation of a value attitude to their health. The use of health-saving technologies in physical education lessons, improving the physical condition of students through physical activity, proper nutrition and rest help students become kinder, stronger in spirit, lifts them above their weaknesses, forms a comprehensively developed personality, which is the primary task of any teacher.

The main provisions of the methodology of teaching physical culture. Teaching methods that are the most effective in the pedagogical practice of a physical education teacher.

Physical culture is an integral part of general culture, a sphere of socio-

cultural activity, which is a set of spiritual and material values created and used by society for the purpose of physical development of a person, improvement of his motor activity, aimed at strengthening his health and contributing to the harmonious development of personality.

The structure of the holistic pedagogical process.

1. Training is a process of purposeful transfer of socio-historical experience; organization of the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities.

2. Education is a systematic and purposeful process of influencing human consciousness and behavior in order to form certain attitudes, concepts, principles and value orientations.

3. Education is a process of active acquisition of systematized knowledge, methods of cognitive and subject activity for the purpose of creative development of personality.

The structure of teaching the technique of motor actions is characterized by:

The first stage is preparatory (initial learning). The essence of the stage is to ensure that all

students have the required level of physical and psychological readiness to master new educational material. Teaching methods - a story about the applied meaning of motor actions; conversations, generalized explanations, verbal instructions focused on the formation of the necessary motivation, generalized explanations, verbal instructions.

The second stage is the formation of the ability to perform a motor action in the general scheme (in-depth learning). The essence of the stage is to ensure, on the basis of knowledge and formed basic motor coordination, the ability to perform a motor action as a whole, observing the basis of the technique at least in a rough form.

The third stage is the formation of motor skills (further improvement and automation of the skill). The essence of the stage is the formation of the ability to

perform a motor action with the focus of students' attention on the conditions and the result of the action.

The fourth stage is the consolidation of the mastered movement. It begins after the motor skill has been formed. The essence of the stage is to achieve the stability of performing a motor action.

The fifth stage is the formation of conditions for using knowledge, motor and instructional skills in the process of independent studies. The essence of the stage is expressed in the purposeful and systematic

inclusion of motor actions studied in the lessons, in the content of various forms of manifestation of physical activity of students.

Methods of performing motor actions, with the help of which the motor task is solved expediently, with relatively greater efficiency, it is customary to call the technique of physical exercises (from the Greek root "techne" – skill, art). The degree of effectiveness of the exercise technique does not remain unchanged. It is continuously being improved and updated due to the physical improvement of the person himself, the social practice of physical education, as well as inventory and equipment.

In the practice of physical education and sports training , there are:

The basis of the technique is a set of those links and features of the structure of movements that are certainly necessary to solve a motor task in a certain way (the order of appearance of muscle forces, the main moments of intermuscular contractions in space and time).

The main link of the technique is the most important part of the method of performing a motor task. (In jumping – repulsion; in throwing – final efforts).

The details of the technique are secondary features of the movement that do not violate its main mechanism. The details of the technique can be different for different people and in most cases depend on their individual morphological and functional characteristics (for example, in hurdling, some jump over barriers,

while others step on them).

The main form of organization of educational work on physical education is an educational activity (lesson). A physical education lesson is a mandatory form of classes for all students, providing the necessary minimum of knowledge, skills, and skills provided for in the program. During the lessons, students learn a complex of morning gymnastics, a complex of gymnastics before classes, physical training minutes, various physical exercises, join the elements of sports competitions. The main methods used in the lessons:

1. frontal (exercises are performed simultaneously by all students, its advantage is a large coverage of students, achieving high density and heavy load);
2. on-line (students perform the same exercises in turn one after the other without interruption. It is convenient when performing acrobatic exercises, climbing, jumping);
3. shift (students are divided into shifts, in turn to perform the exercise (some perform, others observe));
4. group (students work independently according to the assignment, performing various types of exercises in order of priority, groups change places);
5. individual (most often used in test lessons, it allows the teacher to sum up after the exercise by the student, pay attention to shortcomings and mistakes)

Methods of teaching, education of motor qualities:

1. The uniform method is characterized by a single continuous operation lasting from several seconds to several hours (for competitive distances).
2. The variable method is characterized by a single continuous operation lasting from several seconds to several hours, depending on the goals and conditions.
3. The repeated method is characterized by the repetition of the same exercises with an interval for rest, during which there is a complete restoration of working capacity.

4. The interval method is characterized by the repetition of the same exercises at certain intervals.

5. The competitive method is characterized by performing exercises in conditions close to competition.

6. The game method is based on the education of motor qualities during the game.

7. The circular method is a continuous, consistent performance of a set of physical exercises. It is called circular because the exercises are performed in a circle consisting of several stations. In physical education lessons, it is necessary to differentiate the approach to students (dosing loads). If the whole class is given the same task, it is necessary to focus on weak students. Then the task will be feasible for everyone.

Thus, there are many different teaching methods that can be divided into: 1. verbal methods (story, explanation, conversation, command and indication, verbal assessments (in the form of approval or disapproval), counting);

2. visual methods (natural visibility, mediated visibility, figurative visibility);

3. practical: methods of strictly regulated exercise and partially regulated exercise.

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